

Spectrophotometric Determination of Phenols in Air

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The present investigation is based on the oxidative coupling reaction of benzidine and phenol using potassium dichromate-potassium ferricyanide as oxidizer in sodium carbonate medium (pH 10.5-11.5). The red dye, extractable in higher alcohols, is used for the determination of submicrogram levels of phenols spectrophotometrically. The purple colour *n*-pentanol extract shows an absorption maxima at 535 nm. Beer's law is followed in the range of 4 to 70 μg phenol. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $3.05 \times 10^4 \text{ l.mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0029 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$, respectively. The optimum reaction conditions for the oxidative colour reaction have been investigated. The method has been successfully applied for analyses of phenols in air.

PHENOL and related compounds are well known for their toxicity and are extensively used in/ emitted from various industries and may occur in domestic waste water, industrial effluent and drinking water supplies^{1,2}. The U. S. Environmental Protection Agency recommends a maximum of 5 ppm (19 mg/m³) for phenols in air.

A number of screening procedures and modifications have been developed to improve the applicability of original analytical methods for the determination of phenol in air³⁻⁸. The commonly used reagents for the determination of phenol are diazotized *p*-nitroaniline³, 2,6-dibromoquinone chlorimide⁴, *p*-aminodimethylamine⁵ and 4-aminoantipyrine⁶. The 4-aminoantipyrine method adopted by the U. S. Environmental Protection Agency as a standard for monitoring phenols suffers from lack of selectivity, variable sensitivity and instability of the dye formed. In the present investigation an extractive spectrophotometric determination of phenols in air has been developed. A method, based on the oxidative coupling reaction of benzidine and phenol using potassium dichromate-potassium ferricyanide couple as oxidizer in sodium carbonate medium (pH 10.5-11.5), was recently reported by us⁹ for the determination of phenol in river water and coke oven aqueous waste. The method is further modified to determine phenol in air. The dye formed is extracted in *n*-pentanol, exhibits an absorption maxima at 535 nm and is stable for 24 hr. The system is free from common interferents including cresols, xylenols and is highly selective and sensitive for phenol. It has been successfully applied for the determination of phenol in air.

Experimental

Carl Zeiss Spekol and ECIL spectrophotometer model GS 865 were used for all spectral measurements using one cm path length cells. pH measurements were made with ECIL digital pH meter, type pH 5651. Fritted midget impingers of 35 ml capacity were used for sampling procedures. Flow rate

adjustable calibrated rotameters were used for flow rate measurements.

A stock solution containing 1 mg/ml phenol was prepared in freshly deaerated double distilled water and was standardized by bromate-bromide method⁷. A working standard of 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ phenol was prepared by appropriate dilution of stock.

0.15 *M* stock solution of oxidiser was prepared by dissolving 4.47 g potassium dichromate, 4.84 g potassium ferricyanide and 4.0 g sodium hydroxide in 100 ml water. 2 ml of the stock was diluted to 100 ml and used as a working solution.

5.62 g sodium carbonate dissolved in 500 ml glass distilled water (pH was 11.5), 1×10^{-3} *M* solution of benzidine in water and 10% w/v aqueous solution of disodium salt of EDTA were used. 10 ml of the sodium carbonate solution was used as absorbing solution for phenol.

AnalaR grade chemicals were used.

Procedure : Air was drawn at the rate of 1 l/min through two impingers (connected in series) each containing 10 ml sodium carbonate solution for collection of phenol. After sampling, the absorbing solution was quantitatively transferred to a 250 ml separatory funnel. The pH of the solution was adjusted by addition of sodium carbonate solution and 4 ml of the oxidizer was added. After shaking the flask for 2 min, 2 ml benzidine solution was added. The mixture was kept for 2-5 min for colour development. The red coloured dye was then extracted with 25 ml *n*-pentanol in two portions of 15 and 10 ml each. The absorbance of the purple coloured dye was measured at 535 nm against a reagent blank. Samples with higher concentration were diluted appropriately before determination, while for samples containing phenol in the range of 0.04 to 0.1 mg/lit, the red dye formed was extracted in 10 ml *n*-pentanol. The concentration of phenol was computed from a calibration curve prepared in a similar manner.

Results and Discussion

All spectral studies were made with 100 ml of water containing required amount of phenol. The extracted dye shows an absorption maxima at 535 nm and is stable for 24 hr. The absorbance obtained was independent of temperature over the range 15 to 60°. pH is an important variable and slight change in pH produces considerable change in the colour development. The absorbance, however, was found to be maximum and unaffected in the pH range 10.5 to 11.5. Sodium carbonate was found to be the most suitable for attaining the required pH. At least 4 ml of the oxidizer and 10 fold molar excess of benzidine were necessary for full colour development. The reaction is independent of time as constant absorbance values were obtained for time range 2 to 60 min.

The colour reaction was found to obey Beer's law in the range 0.04 to 0.70 ppm (for concentration from 0.04 ppm to 0.25 ppm, the extraction was done in 10 ml *n*-pentanol whereas higher concentration was extracted in 25 ml). The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be 3.05×10^4 l. mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.0029 µg/cm², respectively. Reproducibility of the method for evaporation was evaluated and the standard deviation as well as relative standard deviation were found to be ±0.18 µg and 0.6% respectively (Table 1).

TABLE 1—REPRODUCIBILITY OF THE METHOD

No. of days	Concentration of phenol taken per determination = 30 µg	
	Concentration of phenol obtained* µg	
1	29.90	
2	30.30	
3	30.20	
4	30.00	
5	29.85	
6	30.00	
7	30.25	

*Mean of five repetitive analysis.
Standard deviation = ±0.18 µg
Relative standard deviation = ±0.6%

Collection efficiency: The collection efficiency of sodium carbonate was studied by passing the purified air through a phenol evaporation chamber preheated to 60-70°. Known amounts of phenol were evaporated from the chamber and were absorbed in the solution. Nearly 100% absorption was achieved by taking two impingers with 10 ml of absorbing solution at a flow rate of 1 l/min. The effect of flow rate was studied by carrying out sampling at different flow rates and it was observed that collection of phenol in the first impinger decreased with the increase in flow rate. Thus flow of 1 l/min was found to be the best suitable.

Effect of interferents: A specific study was carried out to see the effects of interferents commonly present with phenol. The effect was studied

by adding known amounts of interferents to 100 ml water containing 0.2 ppm of phenol. Similar studies were also carried out by adding known amounts of interferents to the absorbing solution and collecting phenol. The tolerance limit of interferents, shown in Table 2, are the amount of interferents that

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF INTERFERENTS
Concentration of phenol = 20 µg* (0.2 ppm)

Interferents	Tolerance limit ppm	Tolerance limit** ppm
Mg(II), Pb(II), Fe(II)	10	50
Zr(II), Cd(II), Bi(II) ^a , Fe(III) ^a	25	100
Ag(II), Sr(II), Ca(II), Ba(II), Li(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Sb(III), As(III), B(II), Zr(IV), Be(II), Cu(II).	50	150
Mo(VI), W(VI), Al(III), Mg(II), Mn(II)	100	100
CH ₃ COO ⁻ , SCN ⁻ , PO ₄ ³⁻ , SO ₄ ²⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻ , SiO ₃ ²⁻	500	—
Aniline, naphthalene, HCHO, pyridine, 3,4-xyleneol, 2,4-xyleneol	50	—
<i>o</i> -Cresol	60	—
<i>m</i> -Cresol	80	—
<i>p</i> -Cresol, <i>p</i> -chlorophenol, <i>p</i> -nitrophenol	100	—
<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol	50	—

* The absorbing solution diluted to 100 ml containing the above amount of ions was used for study.

** Masked by 1 ml of 10% w/v EDTA solution.

a Masked by 1 ml of 10% sod. pot. tartrate solution.

cause an error within ±2% in the determination of phenol. Effect of other phenols showed that upto 60 ppm of *o*-cresol, a major co-pollutant, caused no error but higher amounts gave low absorbance value along with brown colour. For *m*-cresol, the limit was 80 ppm and for *p*-cresol it was 100 ppm. Interference from formaldehyde and sulphur can be removed as reported in literature¹⁰.

Comparison with conventional method and other methods:

To check the validity of the method, analytical values obtained by the proposed method were compared with those obtained by the conventional aminoantipyrine method. Results in Table 3 show

TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF PHENOL IN AIR*

Method I** Benzidine + phenol Proposed method ppm	Method II** 4-Amino-antipyrine + phenol Conventional method ppm
5.65	5.60
3.80	3.82
2.96	2.92
4.29	4.27
12.71	12.73
14.05	14.01
16.07	16.03

* Synthetic samples prepared in the lab. were analysed by the recommended procedure.

** Mean of five replicates.

that the values are almost identical to that of conventional method. It can thus be concluded that the proposed method is satisfactory for practical analysis of phenol in air. The method can also

TABLE 4—COMPARISON WITH OTHER METHODS

	Gibbs method	Nitrosophenol method	4-Aminoantipyrine method	Benzidine method
References	4, 12, 13	14	3, 7	Present method
Special reagent	Borate buffer, 2,6-dibromoquinone chloride	Acetic acid, potassium hydroxide	4-Aminoantipyrine, potassium ferricyanide	Sodium carbonate buffer, potassium dichromate, ferricyanide
Concentration range ppm	0-10	0-10	0.1-2.0	0.1-0.7
Interferences	Sulphides, reducing agents, thiocresol	Inorganic salts, aniline, xyldine	Sulphur compounds, metallic ions	Sulphur compounds
Standard deviation	1.03	1.45	0.002	0.005
Colour	Blue	Orange-yellow	Red	Purple
λ_{max} , nm	670	420	510	595
Stability	—	—	30 min	24 hr
Dye formed	Indophenol dye	Nitrosophenol dye	Antipyrine red dye	Indaniline dye

be favourably compared with other methods reported for determination of phenol in air^{3,4,7,11-14} (Table 4).

The method reported here is simple, rapid and sensitive. Only 5-10 min are required after sampling for full colour development. The dye formed is stable for 24 hr. The method has been successfully applied for routine analysis of phenol in air.

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